

1 **Table S1**

2 **References for subunits of the TOM, TOB/SAM and ERMES complexes used in BLAST**
 3 **search.**

4
5

Protein	Accession number and organism
Tom5	<p>Fungi: EGX93488 <i>C. militaris</i>, EAA35832 <i>N. crassa</i>, EMS22290 <i>R. toruloides</i>, EDN61253 <i>S. cerevisiae</i>, G2TRP7 <i>S. pombe</i> Viridiplantae: NP_196421 <i>A. thaliana</i>, EDP08420 <i>C. reinhardtii</i>, EOY22084 <i>T. cacao</i>, P08196 <i>S. lycopersicum</i> Metazoa: A8YXZ8 <i>B. taurus</i>, EGV92195 <i>C. griseus</i>, NP_001127956 <i>H. sapiens</i>, ADO28137 <i>I. punctatus</i>, AFI37119 <i>M. mulatta</i>, B1AXP6 <i>M. musculus</i>, EPQ18733 <i>M. brandtii</i>, Q5R676 <i>P. abelii</i>, ELW69860 <i>T. chinensis</i></p>
Tom6	<p>Fungi: EJP66545 <i>B. bassiana</i>, CCG25521 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i>, CBF82512 <i>E. nidulans</i>, EKD21409 <i>M. brunnea</i>, Efy91581 <i>M. acridum</i>, EDP48137 <i>N. fumigata</i>, AAK18811 <i>N. crassa</i>, EKV11557 <i>P. digitatum</i>, EEA18753 <i>P. marseffii</i>, CAA99236 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> Metazoa: AAW82111 <i>B. taurus</i>, BAG30996 <i>H. sapiens</i>, AFE76132 <i>M. mulatta</i>, NP_079641 <i>M. musculus</i>, ELK00312 <i>P. alecto</i>, ELW66052 <i>T. chinensis</i> Viridiplantae: NP_564545 <i>A. thaliana</i>, EEE85918 <i>P. trichocarpa</i></p>
Tom7	<p>Amoebozoa: Q54RZ5, <i>D. discoideum</i>, EFA78398 <i>P. pallidum</i> Fungi: A1CM16 <i>A. clavatus</i>, Q3MPF4 <i>C. albicans</i>, E3QAN6 <i>C. graminicola</i>, C8V010 <i>E. nidulans</i>, E5ABA6 <i>L. muculans</i>, Q9C1J0 <i>N. crassa</i>, A1DM09 <i>N. fischeri</i>, B6QV75 <i>P. marseffii</i>, A6ZS10 <i>S. cerevisiae</i>, B6K4E6 <i>S. japonicus</i>, CBQ67540 <i>S. reilianum</i>, F2PV03 <i>T. equinum</i> Metazoa: E2GEZ0 <i>B. taurus</i>, A8NG07 <i>B. malayi</i>, P34660 <i>C. elegans</i>, C1BNP2 <i>C. rogercresseyi</i>, E2AYL4 <i>C. floridanus</i>, B0X856 <i>C. quinquefasciatus</i>, Q7K036 <i>D. melanogaster</i>, C1BW89 <i>E. Lucius</i>, E2C311 <i>H. saltator</i>, Q75MR5 <i>H. sapiens</i>, C1BFD2 <i>O. mykiss</i>, C1BJ96 <i>O. mordax</i>, E0VJA3 <i>P. humanus subsp. Corporis</i>, D3ZMR1 <i>R. norvegicus</i>, B9EM79 <i>S. salar</i>, B5G498 <i>T. guttata</i>, E2J7F8 <i>T. matogrossensis</i>, A9JSP9 <i>X. tropicalis</i> Opisthokonta: E9C1N2 <i>C. owczarzaki</i> Viridiplantae: Q3EC17 <i>A. thaliana</i>, A8IG88 <i>C. reinhardtii</i>, B9NKR7 <i>P. trichocarpa</i>, B9SC98 <i>R. communis</i>, O82067 <i>S. tuberosum</i>, Q6DL92 <i>T. aestivum</i>, B6SJ3R3 <i>Z. mays</i></p>
Tom20	<p>Fungi: EER40887 <i>A. capsulatus</i>, CCG22491 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i>, EFW13694 <i>C. posadasii</i>, ACF06613 <i>E. guineensis</i>, CCA39581 <i>K. pastoris</i>, GAC72562 <i>P. antarctica</i>, EEH18555 <i>P. brasiliensis</i>, CCO31903 <i>R. solani</i>, EMS22925 <i>R. toruloides</i>, CAA97084 <i>S. cerevisiae</i>, EGD95676 <i>T. tonsurans</i>, CCH45357 <i>W. ciferrii</i> Metazoa: XP_001652747 <i>A. aegypti</i>, ADY43237 <i>A. suum</i>, NP_001092653 <i>B. taurus</i>, A8Y3V5 <i>C. briggsae</i>, Q19766 <i>C. elegans</i>, EMC86060 <i>C. livia</i>, EMP27268 <i>C. mydas</i>, EDS31058 <i>C. quinquefasciatus</i>, GAA35186 <i>C. sinensis</i>, EHJ74209 <i>D. plexippus</i>, NP_001002698 <i>D. rerio</i>, ACO14271 <i>E. lucius</i>, ADD20139 <i>G. morsitans</i>, ADD38509 <i>L. salmonis</i>, NP_077176 <i>M. musculus</i>, AAL05599 <i>M. unguiculatus</i>, NP_001135431 <i>N. vitripennis</i>, AFJ91791 <i>O. edulis</i>, ELK05097 <i>P. alecto</i>, NP_690918 <i>R. norvegicus</i>, ACM09147 <i>S. salar</i>, ELW68132 <i>T. chinensis</i>, AAH76705 <i>X. (Silurana) tropicalis</i>, NP_001080323 <i>X. laevis</i> Stramenopiles: CBJ27905 <i>E. siliculosus</i> Viridiplantae: EMT00308 <i>A. tauschii</i>, AAK64184 <i>A. thaliana</i>, ABF74690 <i>H. brasiliensis</i>, AEST2042 <i>M. truncatula</i>, A2WYG9 <i>O. sativa</i>, XP_003082381 <i>O. tauri</i>, CAA63223 <i>S. tuberosum</i>, EMS57714 <i>T. urartu</i>, AFW84136 <i>Z. mays</i>, ACG30214 <i>Z. mays</i></p>
Tom22	<p>Fungi: EER37412 <i>H. capsulatus</i>, XP_002620115 <i>B. dermatitidis</i>, XP_003017458 <i>A. benhamiae</i>, XP_001269087 <i>A. clavatus</i>, KEY79581 <i>A. fumigatus</i>, CAE47910 <i>A. fumigatus</i>, XP_710764 <i>C. albicans</i>, XP_001239444 <i>C. immitis</i>, XP_003196226 <i>C. gattii</i>, XP_384291 <i>F. graminearum</i>, EFX03100 <i>G. clavigera</i>, XP_002491829 <i>K. pastoris</i>, XP_956695 <i>N. crassa</i>, XP_001264575 <i>N. fischeri</i>, EEH38491 <i>P. lutzii</i>, P49334 <i>S. cerevisiae</i>, O13813 <i>S. pombe</i>, EGD96435 <i>T. tonsurans</i>, EGY19429 <i>V. dahliae</i> Choanoflagellida: EGD79841 <i>S. rosetta</i> Metazoa: XP_003221021 <i>A. carolinensis</i>, DAA34785 <i>A. variegatum</i>, AAI49340 <i>B. taurus</i>, CCD65583 <i>C. elegans</i>, XP_852619 <i>C. I. familiaris</i>, EFN74091 <i>C. floridanus</i>, EGW01687 <i>C. griseus</i>, GAA56922 <i>C. sinensis</i>, AAF241222 <i>D. melanogaster</i>, AAI53451 <i>D. rerio</i>, ADD18896 <i>G. m. morsitans</i>, EHB02205 <i>H. glaber</i>, EHN83430 <i>H. saltator</i>, BAB16408 <i>H. sapiens</i>, XP_003419809 <i>L. africana</i>, XP_010709228 <i>M. gallopavo</i>, NP_064628 <i>M. mulatta</i>, NP_766197 <i>M. musculus</i>, AES08601 <i>M. furo</i>, XP_003264803 <i>N. leucogenys</i>, ACO09752 <i>O. mordax</i>, XP_002831181 <i>P. abelii</i>, EEB15197 <i>P. humanus</i>, XP_001163726 <i>P. troglodytes</i>, NP_997679 <i>R. norvegicus</i>, XP_003771053 <i>S. harrisi</i>, ACM08673 <i>S. salar</i>, XP_003126064 <i>S. scrofa</i>, NP_001039252 <i>X. tropicalis</i> Viridiplantae: XP_002892196 <i>A. lyrata</i>, XP_003078090 <i>O. tauri</i>, NP_001241795 <i>Z. mays</i>, XP_002301850 <i>P. trichocarpa</i>, XP_002272982 <i>V. vinifera</i></p>
Tom40	<p>Alveolata: CAG24986 <i>P. falciparum</i> Amoebozoa: ADZ24223 <i>A. castellanii</i>, XP_642798 <i>D. discoideum</i>, XP_004352318 <i>D. fasciculatum</i>, EFA80126 <i>P. pallidum</i> Cryptophyta: EKX33332 <i>G. theta</i> CCMP2712 Fungi: Q5AH14 <i>C. albicans</i>, AET97826 <i>N. bombycis</i>, P24391 <i>N. crassa</i>, W6QMH2 <i>P. roqueforti</i>, P23644 <i>S. cerevisiae</i>, O13656 <i>S. pombe</i> Haptophyceae: EOD14807 <i>E. huxleyi</i> CCMP1516 Metazoa: Q18090 <i>C. elegans</i>, Q9U4L6 <i>D. melanogaster</i>, A126L1 <i>D. melanogaster</i>, O96008 <i>H. sapiens</i>, BAL42839 <i>M. crassicauda</i>, B5X251 <i>S. salar</i>, B5X9H3 <i>S. salar</i>, Q6P825 <i>X. tropicalis</i> Rhodophyta: BAM79444 <i>C. merolae strain 10D</i> Stramenopiles: CBJ27101 <i>E. siliculosus</i>, EWM29712 <i>N. Gaditana</i> Trimastix: ABW76113 <i>T. pyriformis</i> Viridiplantae: KFM28529 <i>A. protothecoides</i>, Q9LHE5 <i>A. thaliana</i>, Q9SX55 <i>A. thaliana</i>, CCO66139 <i>B. prasinos</i>, XP_008453929 <i>C. melo</i>, EDP06354 <i>C. reinhardtii</i>, EFN52297 <i>C. variabilis</i>, NP_001242605 <i>G. max</i>, KDD73653 <i>Helicosporidium sp. ATCC 50920</i>, XP_008359999 <i>M. domestica</i>, ACO68486 <i>M. sp. RCC299</i>, XP_006644056 <i>O. brachyantha</i>, ABO95318 <i>O. lucimarinus</i> CCE9901, Q10M45 <i>O. sativa subsp. japonica</i>, XP_008779040 <i>P. dactylifera</i>, XP_008790463 <i>P. dactylifera</i>, XP_008792477 <i>P. dactylifera</i>, XP_008221088 <i>P. mume</i>, JAC84130 <i>Tetraselmis sp. GSL018</i>, EFX44900 <i>V. carteri f. nagariensis</i>, XP_008655478 <i>Z. mays</i>, XP_008658595 <i>Z. mays</i></p>
Tom70	<p>Fungi: CCG25000 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i>, EIF49158 <i>D. bruxellensis</i>, AAO32536 <i>N. castellii</i>, AAD21979 <i>N. crassa</i>, EAL87263 <i>N. fumigata</i>, CAA75047 <i>P. anserina</i>, ABN58618 <i>S. cerevisiae</i>, O14217 <i>S. pombe</i> Metazoa: EGI57310 <i>A. echinator</i>, NP_001068796 <i>B. taurus</i>, EKC37920 <i>C. gigas</i>, AAF53148 <i>D. melanogaster</i>, O94826 <i>H. sapiens</i>, AAI39421 <i>M. musculus</i>, BAD11366 <i>R. norvegicus</i> Stramenopiles: CBK23055 <i>B. hominis</i>, ADL28121 <i>B. sp. Nandli</i>, CBJ31076 <i>E. siliculosus</i>, AA032537 <i>N. castellii</i></p>
Metaxin1	<p>Metazoa: EGI63220 <i>A. echinator</i>, NP_001156282 <i>A. pisum</i>, EDP36824 <i>B. malayi</i>, ELR54251 <i>B. mutus</i>, A8XWD1 <i>C. briggsae</i>, O45503 <i>C. elegans</i>, EFN67703 <i>C. floridanus</i>, EKC20634 <i>C. gigas</i>, Q9VHB6 <i>D. melanogaster</i>, NP_001007281 <i>D. rerio</i>, EHB07315 <i>H. glaber</i>, Q13505 <i>H. sapiens</i>, EAW53108 <i>H. sapiens</i>, NP_942584 <i>H. sapiens</i>, Q4R310 <i>M. fascicularis</i>, AFE70029 <i>M. mulatta</i>, NP_001155296 <i>M. musculus</i>, NP_038632 <i>M. musculus</i>, P47802 <i>M. musculus</i>, EDLA15228 <i>M. musculus</i>, AES02372 <i>M. putorius furo</i>, XP_003701385 <i>M. rotundata</i>, ELK02789 <i>P. alecto</i>, EEB16319 <i>P. humanus</i>, XP_003308483 <i>P. troglodytes</i>, NP_001094137 <i>R. norvegicus</i>, EDM00659 <i>R. norvegicus</i>, ACI33431 <i>S. salar</i>, BAF91494 <i>S. scrofa</i>, NP_001084470 <i>X. laevis</i>, AAI35683 <i>X. tropicalis</i></p>

Metaxin2	Metazoa: NP_001094710 <i>B. taurus</i> , ABC33802 <i>C. elegans</i> , ACO10187 <i>C. rogercresseyi</i> , ACU32593 <i>C. millii</i> , EFN60236 <i>C. floridanus</i> , EKC43002 <i>C. gigas</i> , EGW02671 <i>C. griseus</i> , AFJ50577 <i>C. adamanteus</i> , AAP96761 <i>D. rerio</i> , EFN76553 <i>H. saltator</i> , EAX11078 <i>H. sapiens</i> , EAX11076 <i>H. sapiens</i> , EAX11077 <i>H. sapiens</i> , ADO28229 <i>I. furcatus</i> , ADO29224 <i>I. punctatus</i> , EFO23963 <i>L. loa</i> , AFP99270 <i>L. intermedia</i> , AFE64149 <i>M. mulatta</i> , AAY21064 <i>M. musculus</i> , AES02373 <i>M. putorius furo</i> , ELK32717 <i>M. davidii</i> , ELK04731 <i>P. alecto</i> , EDL79192 <i>R. norvegicus</i> , ACI69201 <i>S. salar</i> , NP_001134863 <i>S. salar</i> , NP_001038006 <i>S. scrofa</i> , ACH43784 <i>T. guttata</i> , NP_001098699 <i>T. rubripes</i> , ELW64130 <i>T. chinensis</i> , NP_001084472 <i>X. laevis</i> , AAT57871 <i>X. tropicalis</i>
Tob38/ Sam35	Fungi: EAL90650 <i>A. fumigatus</i> , CBF89045 <i>A. nidulans</i> , CCD44290 <i>B. cinerea</i> , CCG24718 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i> , EFW90049 <i>M. acridum</i> , EAW22545 <i>N. fischeri</i> , P14693 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , EFE39159T. <i>verrucosum</i> Stramenopiles: CBJ32432 <i>E. siliculosus</i>
Mas37/ Sam37	Fungi: EAW11375 <i>A. clavatus</i> , GAD92478 <i>B. spectabilis</i> , EAL03688 <i>C. albicans</i> , XP_002418173 <i>C. dubliniensis</i> , EFW15805 <i>C. posadasii</i> , EXV02056 <i>M. robertsii</i> , EAW18120 <i>N. fischeri</i> , EKV09579 <i>P. digitatum</i> , P50110 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , EED15167 <i>T. stipitatus</i> Metazoa: ADD20070 <i>G. morsitans</i>
Tob55/ Sam50	Amoebozoa: model from: Wojtkowska et al. 2010 from <i>A. castellanii</i> Fungi: EED44828 <i>A. flavus</i> NRRL3357, EAL84610 <i>A. fumigatus</i> Af293, CBF79308 <i>A. nidulans</i> FGSC A4, CCD45409 <i>B. cinerea</i> T4, CCG25583 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i> , CBY00086 <i>L. maculans</i> , JN3AAS76651 <i>N. crassa</i> , EKV15900 <i>P. digitatum</i> PHI26, EDN62785 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> YJM789, EPY52358 <i>S. cryophilus</i> OY26, EEB06890 <i>S. japonicus</i> yFS275, EPX73056 <i>S. octosporus</i> yFS286, CAA97352 <i>S. pombe</i> , ABN68113 <i>S. stipitatus</i> CBS 6054, EEA24609 <i>T. marneffeii</i> ATCC 18224, EED18370 <i>T. stipitatus</i> ATCC 10500 Metazoa: JAB65435 <i>A. glabripennis</i> , JAC44697 <i>B. dorsalis</i> , JAB85363 <i>C. capitata</i> , AAC72375 <i>D. melanogaster</i> , Q9V784 <i>D. melanogaster</i> , Q9Y512 <i>H. sapiens</i> , JAA88618 <i>P. aegeria</i> , EEB19878 <i>P. humanus corporis</i> , CCD81062 <i>S. mansoni</i> , ACI66168 <i>S. salar</i> , ACI33501 <i>S. salar</i> , NP_001083329 <i>X. laevis</i> Stramenopiles: CBJ33514 <i>E. siliculosus</i> Viridiplantae: EMT14957 <i>A. tauschii</i> , EEF48875 <i>R. communis</i> , EEF41943 <i>R. communis</i> , EEF34085 <i>R. communis</i> , EMS50338 <i>T. urartu</i>
Mdm10	Fungi: EJP66870 <i>B. bassiana</i> , C4YIG3 <i>C. albicans</i> , EAU84591 <i>C. cinerea</i> , ADV25733 <i>C. gattii</i> , ELA31908 <i>C. gloeosporioides</i> , AAW47220 <i>C. neoformans</i> , CCG21274 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i> , CCE32471 <i>C. purpurea</i> , CCA36709 <i>K. pastoris</i> , CAA75046 <i>P. anserina</i> , AAC04947 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , DAA06978 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , CAE00796 <i>S. macrospora</i> , ELU45447 <i>T. cucumeris</i> , EEEY14339 <i>V. alfalfae</i> , EGY13374 <i>V. dahliae</i>
Mdm12	Fungi: C0NF00 <i>A. capsulatus</i> , A1CNY1 <i>A. clavatus</i> , C5GK63 <i>A. dermatitidis</i> , B8MZJ8 <i>A. flavus</i> , Q75CC2 <i>A. gossypii</i> , Q5BF59 <i>A. nidulans</i> , A2QAU8, <i>A. niger</i> , Q2UQG9 <i>A. oryzae</i> , C5FUT6 <i>A. otae</i> , Q0CZL5 <i>A. terreus</i> , A6RLP9 <i>B. fuckeliana</i> , Q59S52 <i>C. albicans</i> , A8NEF5 <i>C. cinerea</i> okayama, B9WK07 <i>C. dubliniensis</i> , Q6FVF2 <i>C. glabrata</i> , Q2HDE7 <i>C. globosum</i> , Q1E2F1 <i>C. immitis</i> , C4YBT3 <i>C. lusitaniae</i> , B5RUL6 <i>D. hansenii</i> , Q6CUC3 <i>K. lactis</i> , C4R415 <i>K. pastoris</i> , B0DQ09 <i>L. bicolor</i> , A5E771 <i>L. elongisporus</i> , C5DEN8 <i>L. thermotolerans</i> , A8PSC0 <i>M. globosa</i> , A5DAR4 <i>M. guilliermondii</i> , A4RM00 <i>M. oryzae</i> , Q7SEZ6 <i>N. crassa</i> , A1D1T8 <i>N. fischeri</i> , Q4WRX2 <i>N. fumigata</i> , B2AA87 <i>P. anserina</i> , B6HAR6 <i>P. chrysogenum</i> , C1H3V1 <i>P. lutzii</i> , B6QAV0 <i>P. marneffeii</i> , Q0U1X7 <i>P. nodorum</i> , B8P9E4 <i>P. placenta</i> , B2W543 <i>P. tritici-repentis</i> , B3LJ47 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , B6K4Z5 <i>S. japonicas</i> , Q92377 <i>S. pombe</i> , A7ELE2 <i>S. sclerotiorum</i> , A3LWH1 <i>S. stipites</i> , XP_003232252 <i>T. rubrum</i> , B8M2V6 <i>T. stipitatus</i> , Q4PEB4 <i>U. maydis</i> , C4JY59 <i>U. reesii</i> , A7TFP8 <i>V. polyspora</i> , C5DTC4 <i>Z. rouxii</i>
Mdm34/ Mmm2	Fungi: C0NY51 <i>A. capsulatus</i> , C5JVU4 <i>A. dermatitidis</i> , C5FRB0 <i>A. otae</i> , A1CHU1 <i>A. clavatus</i> , A2QJH4 <i>A. niger</i> , Q2UJF5 <i>A. oryzae</i> , Q0CZY7 <i>A. terreus</i> , A6S9E2 <i>B. fuckeliana</i> , C4YE34 <i>C. albicans</i> , B9W824 <i>C. dubliniensis</i> Q6FQE0 <i>C. glabrata</i> CCG21585 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i> , Q2H9Y1 <i>C. globosum</i> , C4Y6F4 <i>C. lusitaniae</i> , Q1E4T3 <i>C. immitis</i> , A8NYS9 <i>C. cinerea</i> , P0C071 <i>C. neoformans</i> , Q5BBM5 <i>E. nidulans</i> , C4QYM9 <i>K. pastoris</i> , B0CXH5 <i>L. bicolor</i> , A5DUL5 <i>L. elongisporus</i> , A4QT54 <i>M. oryzae</i> , A8QD14 <i>M. globosa</i> , A5DLK4 <i>M. guilliermondii</i> , A1CWW9 <i>N. fischeri</i> , B0Y614 <i>N. fumigata</i> , Q7RZK9 <i>N. crassa</i> , C0S713 <i>P. brasiliensis</i> , B6QIB3 <i>P. marneffeii</i> , B2VS19 <i>P. tritici-repentis</i> , EJS43835 <i>S. arboricola</i> , B3LHR1 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , A7EWF5 <i>S. sclerotiorum</i> , B8MKT9 <i>T. stipitatus</i> , C4JQ45 <i>U. reesii</i> , Q4PFAT <i>U. maydis</i> , Q6C7W0 <i>Y. lipolytica</i>
Mmm1	Fungi: EEH03033 <i>A. capsulatus</i> , EFR03467 <i>A. gypseum</i> , GAA86306 <i>A. kawachii</i> , EJP62622 <i>B. bassiana</i> , CCG23843 <i>C. orthopsilosis</i> , CCA40584 <i>K. pastoris</i> , EDK46090 <i>L. elongisporus</i> , AAF43713 <i>N. crassa</i> , EDP47543 <i>N. fumigata</i> , EEH50174 <i>P. brasiliensis</i> , EDU40624 <i>P. tritici-repentis</i> , CAA97449 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , EEB09187 <i>S. japonicas</i> , BAA21458 <i>S. pombe</i>
Gem1	Amoebozoa: XP_647338 <i>D. discoideum</i> , EGG25101 <i>D. fasciculatum</i> , F1A505 <i>D. purpureum</i> , EFA85557 <i>P. pallidum</i> Fungi: Q758X6 <i>A. gossypii</i> , Q2UM43 <i>A. oryzae</i> , Q5ABR2 <i>C. albicans</i> , Q6FIR8 <i>C. glabrata</i> , P0C078 <i>C. neoformans</i> , Q5B5L3 <i>E. nidulans</i> , Q4I2W2 <i>G. zeae</i> , XP_006966705 <i>T. reesei</i> QM6a, Q6CY37 <i>K. lactis</i> , Q7RZA2 <i>N. crassa</i> , Q4WN24 <i>N. fumigata</i> , W6QF87 <i>P. roqueforti</i> , P39722 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> , O59781 <i>S. pombe</i> , Q4PB75 <i>U. maydis</i> , Q6C2J1 <i>Y. lipolytica</i> Metazoa: Q94180 <i>C. elegans</i> , Q8IMX7 <i>D. melanogaster</i> , Q298L5 <i>D. pseudoobscura</i> <i>pseudoobscura</i> , Q6NVC5 <i>D. rerio</i> , Q5ZM73 <i>G. gallus</i> , Q5ZM83 <i>G. gallus</i> , Q8IXI2 <i>H. sapiens</i> , Q8IXI1 <i>H. sapiens</i> , Q8BG51 <i>M. musculus</i> , Q7TSA0 <i>R. norvegicus</i> , XP_791124 <i>S. purpuratus</i> , Q864R5 <i>S. scrofa</i> , Q6DIS1 <i>X. tropicalis</i> Opisthokonta: EFW47272 <i>C. owczarzaki</i> Viridiplantae: Q8RFXF8 <i>A. thaliana</i> , EFJ25633 <i>S. moellendorffii</i>

1 **Figure S1**

2 **Alignments of the identified subunits of the TOM, TOB/SAM and ERMES complexes in**
3 **and their counterparts deposited in the GenBank and displaying differences in amino**
4 **acid sequences.**

5 Red background of letters denotes indels whereas conservative and radical substitutions are
6 marked by blue and green background, respectively.

7

8

9

10

11

12

13

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23

24

25

26

27

28

29

30

31

32

33

A. castellanii Tom70

```

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      MEAKVKEANALFLQGKHS PAVALYTA AIEA-----GAAYLRLGLYRKCLADCEA
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    MEAKVKEANALFLQGKHS PAVALYTA AIEAGSPTATLLCNRGAAYLRLGLYRKCLADCEA
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      ALRLQPADPRPYLLK GKALVGMNKSADAEAAWRAGLDKADGAADV ELLQLQGQLNPPVA
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    ALRLQAADPRPYLLK GKALVGMNKSADAEAAWRAGLDKADGAADV ELLQLQGQLNPPVA
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      APAIATAPAASSEPKPAVITNGEAKATITTPSPQASAVPRAAEPAGKTKSPAPAQQPKKE
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    APAIATAPAASSEPKPAVITNGE--ATITTPSPQASAVPRAAEPAGKTKSPAPAQQPKKE
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      AKSPPTAAAVAAANPNDLAEASAMVAARGLVQHSGNTTLDEKIAMGYLHVNTGNFPQAI
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    AKSPPTAAAVAAANPNDLAEASAMVAARGLVQHSGNTTLDEKIAMGYLHVNTGNFPQAI
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      KLFNVLVNLYPKLVAA YLGRGTAYALSGHLSTAVEEFSAAIKIDDTCEAWKRRGQSRAA
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    KLFNVLVNLYPKLVAA YLGRGTAYALSGHLSTAVEEFSAAIKIDDTCEAWKRRGQSRAA
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      MGQDAEAVLDLTRA AEELAPKDADIYHQRLIYFKLRNYGRAAE DFRRATAADAMSKLSWN
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    MGQDTEAVLDLTRA AEELAPKDADIYHQRLIYFKLRNYGRAAE DFRRATAADAMSKLSWN
****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      HLGLCLNALGRPMEAI QAHKRALELDPAFREALANIGQAYKDYGN SLKAEKYFAKGLKVD
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    HLGLCLNALGRPMEAI HAHKRALELDPAFREALANIGQAYKDYGN SLKAEKYFAKGLKVD
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      PNYMHAFHLRGLARFGAGDHRGALSDFTAALRVDDKHKDSRLMRGIVLHGLGRF REAVAD
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    PNYMHAFHLRGLARFGAGDHRGALSDFTAALRVDDKHKDSRLMRGIVLHGLGRF REAVAD
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      YDVLVREKPDHVAWYNRQIALWTHHHLDT PVAHFNIDRVLNAYFKEAWCKRLDPATLTSY
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    YDVLVREKPDHVAWYNRQIALWTHHHLDT PVAHFNIDRVLNAYFKEAWCKRLDPATLTSY
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      TSQPPINNAIADVALNDEL RSEHAKLLIRAAVDIGKKIQLNCPGYLANQRQQRACGF AII
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    TSQPPINNAIADVALNDEL RSEHAKLLIRAAVDIGKKIQLNCPGYLANQRQQRACGF AII
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      ELAQLRRVWAGEETQLSGKASSLTDQPHTFAWRDLYDIPIRWRQFSEPNDPVWVVDLLS
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    ELAQLRRVWAGEETQLSGKASSLTDQPHTFAWRDLYDIPIRWRQFSEPNDPVWVVDLLS
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      KTLHEAVQHDFVWVTPCHSLARP NRIMEGTRLTIQRSPP EGYEFSIRTPGTPNRWQEYNA
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    KTLHEAVQHDFVWVTPCHSLARP NRIMEGTRLTIQRSPP EGYEFSIRTPGTPNRWQEYNA
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      EMAHNYRLLQEEASKPHRDL SKLTELVLHMAFYWYNFMPLSRGTA AVGLVTVHAMFLALG
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    EMAHNYRLLQEEASKPDRDQ SKLTELVLHMAFYWYNFMPLSRGTA AVGLVTVHAMFLALG
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      FEMESGLPQGLQPDWEGILTARPSDFVRC LRS AWIDAACRPTTLDALPLVAQVCPTLRH
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    FEMESGLPQGLQPDWEGILTARPSDFVRC LRS AWIDAACRPTTLDALPLVAQVCPTLRH
*****

Tom70_XP_004339622.1      MVLALNAAS
Tom70_Ac_transcriptome    MVLALNAAS
*****

```

37
38
39
40
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53

A. castellanii Tom22 A

```
Tom22_XP_004353494.1 -----MPDPHRYMPHSFLKVDTRLDQWRPALDDAATDA
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome MARPSHHHEFLLLLAVAFLSVGLARQMPDPHRYMPHSFLKVDTRLDQWRPALDDAATDA
*****

Tom22_XP_004353494.1 VRVINSHRPRDQHLALDQVQTDGVQVGRALAFSGTIELADHHHPPHPSAYTFTQHSDFIH
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome VRVINSHRPRDQHLALDQVQTDGVQVGRALAFSGTIELADHHHPPHPSAYTFTQHSDFIH
*****

Tom22_XP_004353494.1 LQPVQPLAPLWALPSPSASLKTEPVDQLPQDEDPVFPEVELEGPLVLHLDQQLYDPVLR
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome LQPVQPLAPLWALPSPSASLKTEPVDQLPQDEDPVFPEVELEGPLVLHLDQQLYDPVLR
*****

Tom22_XP_004353494.1 LPHSVEVGAVRVIRVGPVRLRVGGVVSQMCLRSSLVQQRNIKLLALMDENNATTANLHQQ
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome LPHSVEVGAVRVIRVGPVRLRVGGVVSQMCLRSSLVQQRNIKLLALMDENNATTANLHQQ
*****

Tom22_XP_004353494.1 GEMDVPELELKLVDQGRAFRMWSSSAERVKAKRRSAHVLELLPTAASPSADVSSQVTTTS
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome GEMDVPELELKLVDQGRAFRMWSSSAERVKAKRRSAHVLELLPTAASPSADVSSQVTTTS
*****

Tom22_XP_004353494.1 HGRTDLAPRSASDASLWVLSQANLLRGVIGAFQAQAAEQPVVLRVVEAKAEAVSVLVIP
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome HGRTDLAPRSASDASLWVLSQANLLRGVIGAFQAQAAEQPVVLRVVEAKAEAVSVLVIP
*****

Tom22_XP_004353494.1 MTLREQPHNNHGGKTSQWQVVVTRGADGRHTVTVSHQQLVQQESHVTVAPVWVWANTTTPAV
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome MTLREQPHNNHGGKTSQWQVVVTRGADGRHTVTVSHQQLVQQESHVTVAPVWVWANTTTPAV
*****

Tom22_XP_004353494.1 MRTVQLEKNAHRPAQASS
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome MRTVQLEKNAHRPAQASS
*****
```

Figure S1B

54

A. castellanii Tom22 B

55

Tom22_XP_004358239.1
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome

-----MPDPHRYMPHSFLKVDTTRLDQWRSALDDAATDA
MARTSHHHEFLLLLIVAFLYVGLARQMPDPHRYMPHSFLKVDTTRLDQWRSALDDAATDA

Tom22_XP_004358239.1
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome

VRVLNSHRPRDQHLALDQVQTDGVQVGRALAFSGTIELADHHHPHPSAYTFTQHSDFIH
VRVLNSHRPRDQHLALDQVQTDGVQVGRALAFSGTIELADHHHPHPSAYTFTQHSDFIH

Tom22_XP_004358239.1
Tom22_Ac_transcriptome

LQPVQPLSPLWALPSPSASLKTEPVYQLQPDEDPVFP
LQPVQPLSPLWALPSPSASLKTEPVYQLQPDEDPVFP

57

58

Figure S1C

59

60

61

62

63

64

65

66

67

68

69

70

71

72

73

A. castellanii Metaxin

```

Metaxin_XP_004337900.1      MASSSSSAAPAVLKLHQYGARWELPSFDPFCLSAQAYMRLAGVTFEE-----
Metaxin_Ac_transcriptome    MASSSSSAAPAVLKLHQYGARWELPSFDPFCLSAQAYMRLAGVTFEEVPSNNPDVSPSTN
*****

Metaxin_XP_004337900.1      -----LGDDYVAGTNAIFTYVGNKTGKSLDSALNAEQKATAAAFIHLIETKLHPTLLYNW
Metaxin_Ac_transcriptome    LPLVQLGDDYVAGTNAIFTYVGNKTGKSLDSALNAEQKATAAAFIHLIETKLHPTLLYNW
*****

Metaxin_XP_004337900.1      WAEKQNMGTLLVLPHFNSMVFPLGYVLPRLKQRNVQSYLYTLNLTQDEKVYNDAEECYAA
Metaxin_Ac_transcriptome    WAEKQNMGTLLVLPHFNSMVFPLGYVLPRLKQRNVQSYLYTLNLTQDEKVYNDAEECYAA
*****

Metaxin_XP_004337900.1      LADFLGDKHFFFGD---SLDAVAFGHLAIHLVAPQSHKLSRLLQHKNEAFCKRVMTLY
Metaxin_Ac_transcriptome    LADFLGDKHFFFGDSPSSLDVAFGHLAIHLVAPQSHKLSRLLQHKNEAFCKRVMTLY
*****

Metaxin_XP_004337900.1      FGQDFPAIPAPPATEDKDQKQEMSQHKKTGMYLLTGAGLLILLHYLTKQHQAHHQ
Metaxin_Ac_transcriptome    LGQDFPAIPAPPATEDKDQKQEMSQHKKTGMYLLTGAGLLILLHYLTKQHQAHHQ
:*****

```

74

75

Figure S1D

76

77

78

79

80

81

82

83

84

85

86

87

88

89

90

91

92

93

94

95

A. castellanii Tob55/Sam50

```

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      MSYTDEDEPIDLGVRGEDAWRVRRVWVKGNRRTRPDVVAACVKPVLKARTFDEVLARVAE
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    MSYTDEDEPIDLGVRGEDAWRVRRVWVKGNRRTRPDVVAACVKPVLKARTFDEVLARVAE
*****

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      AAGELKGLGIFKSVNLVLDLDDLPDDVAAADPSACDLRVELVEHKLTRIEVKTSTTVGENEP
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    AAGELKGLGIFKSVNLVLDLDDLPDDVAAADPSACDLRVELVEHKLTRIEVKTSTTVGENEP
*****

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      DVQATVGLCNAPGRAETVSVSAQVGASNWREHWSSAFSLAFKRP-----
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    DVQATVGLCNAPGRAETVSVSAQVGASNWREHWSSAFSLAFKRPVLGQGPGRHIEADAT
*****

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      -----VSYEASARHVIPESSAPLALRSHAGHSLKSAV
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    RASHRLPWCALTQTTHGLALRYSLSHQVSYEASARHVIPESSAPLALRSHAGHSLKSAV
*****

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      KYVYAHDRDDPLTPTTGHAFTSSTELAGLGGDVRVFKQEMAAQLNPLGKTRCSFNVLA
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    KYVYAHDRDDPLTPTTGHAFTSSTELAGLGGDVRVFKQEMAAQLNPLGKTRCSFNVLA
*****

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      KAGYLHALDSGSRI-----RALGGGAYWAGSLHLSFPLP
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    KAGYLHALDSGSRIVDRFFLGGPGSIRGFQYNAVGPESHQQRALGGGAYWAGSLHLSFPLP
*****

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      LRDVPDFVSGHLFANAGNLRQPTPGRSVAANVQDLFSADDVRAAVGAGLVLRMTFGRVEL
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    LRDVPDFVSGHLFANAGNLRQPTPGRSVAANVQDLFSADDVRAAVGAGLVLRMTFGRVEL
*****

Tob55/Sam50_XP_004341043.1      NLSHPIRKAATDLVQPFQVGLSVRFL
Tob55/Sam50_Ac_transcriptome    NLSHPIRKAATDLVQPFQVGLSVRFL
*****

```

97

98

Figure S1E

99

100

101

102

103

104

105

106

107

108

109

110

111

112

113

A. castellanii Gem1

```

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      MKDQVRIVLIGDDGAGKTSLIATLLADSFQEV-----
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    MKDQVRIVLIGDDGAGKTSLIATLLADSFQEVVEQVVPELTIPPSVTNDRVSTHIIDTSS
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      ---HKMDQQLRTADVCLCYAADSENVAERITHWLRHIRHTRQECRAPQVPVILVGNKID
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    RFQHKMDQQLRTADVCLCYAADSENVAERITHWLRHIRHTRQECRAPQVPVILVGNKID
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      LRGEDLTNPQLQEDMEPIMEEFKEVETCIECSAKSFLNVHEVFYFAQRAVLYPTAVLYDA
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    LRGEDLTNPQLQEDMEPIMEEFKEVETCIECSAKSFLNVHEVFYFAQRAVLYPTAVLYDA
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      GRSRLREECVAALKRIFKLCCKDRDGILSDDELNAFQARCFGASLDPAELQGVKDVVRGN
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    GRSRLREECVAALKRIFKLCCKDRDGILSDDELNAFQARCFGASLDPAELQGVKDVVRGN
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      VENGLTEKGLTLTGFLFLHHLFIQKGRLETTWTVLRQFGYDDNLRVDVASLCHSLPAPP
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    VENGLTEKGLTLTGFLFLHHLFIQKGRLETTWTVLRQFGYDDNLRVDVASLCHSLPAPP
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      SHVYELSQAGVAFFSSLHRAFDKGAGLALDDDDLFSTAAPGLPALWTSGELDPATATQL
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    SHVYELSQAGVAFFSSLHRAFDKGAGLALDDDDLFSTAAPGLPALWTSGELDPATATQL
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      NAAHISLRGWLALWSYTTVHDHKTLEYLAWLGFESDPQLALALAKPRREASALLCLVVG
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    NAAHISLRGWLALWSYTTVHDHKTLEYLAWLGFESDPQLALALAKPRREASALLCLVVG
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      PALTDAFLGDFLGKRDHEPSHATSTSITTTTRSPSSRLVALGSLPDISGTEKYVAMRKY
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    PALTDAFLGDFLGKRDHEPSHATSTSITTTTRSPSSRLVALGSLPDISGTEKYVAMRKY
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      LEETEALRTRLHEASLVIVLYDSSDSRSLSNTHAGAELNSLCRNRDTPILHLALHHTAT
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    LEETEALRTRLHEASLVIVLYDSSDSRSLSNTHAGAELNSLCRNRDTPILHLALHHTAT
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      LMLQQDGATVPDLSENGIHLEAFASYSTLLIKAHQQLARREQEWQLPTWPQAALLGAVAV
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    ----DGATVPDLSENGIHLEAFASYSTLLIKAHQQLARREQEWQLPTWPQAALLGAVAV
*****

Gem1_XP_004356731.1      LVGGILLYRHFPGSKQA
Gem1_Ac_transcriptome    LVGGILLYRHFPGSKQA
*****

```

115

116

117

118

119

120

121

122

123

Figure S1F

124 **Figure S2**

125 **Evolutionary analysis of the identified subunits based on Maximum Likelihood analysis.**

126 The RAxML rapid bootstrapping algorithm was used applying 1000 bootstrap replicated. All
127 figures shows unrooted tree. Ac – *A. castellanii*, Ap – *A. proteus*, Dd – *D. discoideum*, Dp –
128 *D. purpureum*, Df – *D. fasciculatum*, Pp – *P. pallidum*, Ed – *E. dispar*, En – *E. nuttalli*.

129 Blue color indicates representatives of Discosea; red color indicates representatives of
130 Tubulinea; green color indicates representatives of Mycetozoa; pink color indicates
131 representatives of Archamoeba. Yellow line indicates Conosa group; light blue color indicates
132 Lobosa.

133

134

135

136

137

138

139

140

141

142

143

144

145

146

147

148

149

150

151

152

153

154

155

156

157

158
159
160
161
163
164
165
166
167
168
169
170
171
172
173
174
175
176
177
178
179
180

Tom20

Figure S2A

181
182
183
184
185
186
187
188
189
190
191
192
193
194
195
196
197
198
199
200
201
202
203
204
205

Tom40

Figure S2B

206
207
208
209
210
211
212
213
214
215
216
217
218
219
220
221
222
223
224
225
226

Tom70

Figure S2C

227
228
229
230
231
232
233
234
235
236
237
238
239
240
241
242
243
244
245
246
247
248
249
250
251

Metaxin

Figure S2D

252
253
254
255
256
257
258

260
261
262
263
264
265
266
267
268
269
270
271

Tob55/Sam50

Figure S2E

272
273
274
275
276
277
278
279
280
281
282
284
285
286
287
288
289
290
291
292
293

Mdm10

Figure S2F

294

Mdm12

295

296

297

298

299

300

301

302

303

304

305

306

307

311

312

313

314

315

316

317

318

Figure S2G

319
320
321
322
323
324
325
326
327
328
329
330
331
332
333
338
339
340
341
342
343
344

Mdm34/Mmm2

Figure S2H

370
371
372
373
374
375
376
377

Gem1

381
382
383
384
385
386
387
388
389
390
391
392

Figure S2J

393 **Figure S3**

394 **Graphical representation of the intron – exon gene structure for the identified subunits**
395 **of the TOM, TOB/SAM and ERMES complexes.** Exons are shown in dark blue whereas
396 introns are showed as black thin lines. Light blue color represents alignments of proteins
397 between species. The lengths of introns were neglected. Ac – *A. castellanii*, Dd – *D.*
398 *discoideum*, Dp – *D. purpureum*, Df – *D. fasciculatum*, Pp – *P. pallidum*, Ed – *E. dispar*, En –
399 *E. nuttalli*

400

401

402

403

404

405

406

407

408

409

410

411

412

413

414

415

416

417

418

419

420

421

422

423

424

425

426

Tom7

427
428
429
430
431
432
433
434
435
436
437
438
439
440
441
442
443
444
445
446
447
448
449
450
451
452
453
454
455
456
457
458

Figure S3A

459

Tom20

460

461

462

463

464

465

466

467

468

469

470

471

472

473

474

475

476

477

478

479

480

481

482

483

484

485

486

487

488

489

490

491

Figure S3B

Tom40

492
493
494
495
496
497
498
499
500
501
502
503
504
505
506
507
508
509
510
511
512
513
514
515
516
517
518
519
520
521
522
523
524

Figure S3C

525
526
527
528
529
530
531
532
533
534
535
536
537
538
539
540
541
542
543
544
545
546
547
548
549
550
551
552
553
554
555
556
557

Tom70

Figure S3D

558

Metaxin

559

560

561

562

563

564

565

566

567

568

Figure S3E

569

570

571

572

573

574

575

576

577

578

579

580

581

582

583

584

585

586

587

588

589

590

591
592
593
594
595
596
597
598
599
600
601
602
603
604
605
606
607
608
609
610
611
612
613
614
615
616
617
618
619
620

Tob55/Sam50

Figure S3F

621
622
623
624
625
626
627
628
629
630
631
632
633
634
635
636
637
638
639
640
641
642
643
644
645
646
647
648
649
650
651
652
653

Mdm10

Figure S3G

Mdm12

654
655
656
657
658
659
660
661
662
663
664
665
666
667
668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676
677
678
679
680
681
682
683
684
685
686

Figure S3H

687
688
689
690
691
692
693
694
695
696
697
698
699
700
701
702
703
704
705
706
707
708
709
710
711
712
713
714
715
716
717
718

Mdm34/Mmm2

Figure S3I

719
720
721
722
723
724
725
726
727
728
729
730
731
732
733
734
735
736
737
738
739
740
741
742
743
744
745
746
747
748
749
750
751

Mmm1

Figure S3J

752

Gem1

753

754

755

756

757

758

759

760

761

762

763

764

765

766

767

768

769

770

771

772

773

774

775

776

777

778

779

780

781

782

783

Figure S3K